

CORPORATE RESTRUCTURING AS AN INSTRUMENT TO ENHANCE SERVICE DELIVERY IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN POST OFFICE IN THE WATERBERG DISTRICT: A CASE OF THE LIMPOPO PROVINCE, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

Globally, Post Offices are experiencing a serious decline in mail volume as well as profit margins. Statistics conclusively show that Post Offices suffered a net loss of R2.5 billion in the 2020–2021 fiscal year, a loss of R1.5 billion in the 2021–2022 fiscal year, and an operating loss of R561 million in the 2022–2023 fiscal year. As a case in point, the South African Post Office (SAPO) is no exception. This article argues that corporate restructuring positively impacts the performance of the South African Post Office. To address this undesirable situation, this article evaluates the impact of restructuring on service delivery at the South African Post Office. This article is based on a study conducted at the South African Post Office in the Waterberg district, which is in the Limpopo province of the Republic of South Africa. Although SAPO endorsed restructuring as a strategy to increase performance, the strategy was found not to be effective, as the entity continuously lost revenue. These findings lay the groundwork for the effective implementation of the South African Post Office restructuring process. The study found that restructuring has a positive impact on service delivery and productivity levels of the South African Post Office. To improve service delivery, the study recommended that restructuring be given priority to bring the ailing entity to stability and sustainability. The study used a mixed-methods approach to collect data. For quantitative data, a questionnaire was used, and for qualitative data, semi-structured interviews were used to solicit data from participants. To select customers, a systematic sampling technique was used, and to select employees, a purposive sampling technique was used. Many of the respondents strongly agreed that corporate restructuring is essential in improving the performance of the Post Office. The article concludes by providing suggestions for the proper implementation of the restructuring process.

Keywords: Restructuring, Corporate, Performance Management, Performance Management System, Revenue, Sustainability, and Service Delivery.

1. Introduction

The study investigated the relationship between restructuring and service delivery in the South African Post Office, Waterberg District in the Limpopo Province. It is a known fact that the South African Post Office branches in the Waterberg district in the Limpopo province are struggling to meet financial obligations, which hurts service delivery. The Post Office suffered a net loss of R2.5 billion in the 2020–2021 fiscal year, a loss of R1.5 billion in the 2021–2022 fiscal year, and an operating loss of R561 million in the 2022–2023 fiscal year, according to SAPO national revenue performance statistics derived from the South African Post Office Corporate Plan (2024,p.48). Umar and Balewa (2023, p.4), regard restructuring as the act of changing the lawful structures of a company to make it more valuable, and it involves a significant modification of the operations of a company. Restructuring the organization ensures optimal and efficient performance (South African Post Office Corporate Plan, 2024 ,p.35). Furthermore, Umar and Balewa (2023,p.1) affirmed that corporate restructuring is a thoughtful overhaul of a troubled entity to restore it to prosperity and an advantage for improved performance. The restructuring program includes redesigning the operating model, reviewing the transport fleet, modernising postal and parcel technologies, and optimizing staff where possible (SAPO Corporate Plan 2024, p.35). It is in this context that corporate restructuring should be implemented to assist the South African Post Office in becoming financially stable.

1. Problem Statement

The Waterberg district's Post Office branches have continuously been losing money. Since this undesirable condition persists, drastic efforts are required to halt the loss and devise strategies to boost its turnover (Balkaran, 2015; Eposi, 2021; Ittmann, 2023). Massive job cutbacks could happen if Waterberg postal branches eventually go bankrupt. In the Waterberg district, where SAPO continues to exhibit a declining turnover pattern, the issues are increasingly apparent. The problem is that although SAPO has a restructuring system in place, the parastatal consistently exhibits low cash flow and a sharp decline in both digital and traditional mail. This downward

trajectory is as a result of ineffective implementation of the restructuring process. In the fiscal year 2023–2024, the South African Post Office nationally showed a decrease in revenue operating profit (loss) of 139 million. Statistics conclusively show that if restructuring is not properly implemented, it has the potential to cause a catastrophe for most organizations. To increase the revenue of the South African Post Office in the Waterberg district, the paper aims to provide suggestions of maximizing profit through an effective restructuring plan. Restructuring has some benefits, and the advantages of restructuring are discussed below as follows:

2. Literature Review

3.1 Advantages of restructuring the organization

3.1.1 Optimization of operations

The South African Post Office will implement initiatives to optimize its operations by digitizing key processes such as revenue protection, tracking and tracking, and delivery management (South African Corporate Plan, 2024,p.35). In my opinion, mail volumes could increase if postal administrators are willing to restructure postal operations. Ittmann (2023) wrote that the global volume ratio of mail to packages decreased from 13:1 in 2005 to 4:1 in 2015 and is expected to reach 1:1 by 2025. This suggests that mail volumes have always been declining yearly, and profit margins have been severely compromised. Restructuring offers new opportunities for companies, which are to be welcomed for the benefits of such restructuring (Mavlutova, Babenko, Dykan, Prokopenko, Kalinichenko and Tokmakova, 2021,p.105). The mail delivery network will be optimized to ensure faster delivery of mail and parcel production items (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024: 37). The continued decline in mail volumes provided one major reason for reform (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023). Due to the recent growth in electronic communication services, which compete with traditional postal services, the volumes in letter mail have been declining, and SAPO has lost significant market share in the highly competitive express and parcel markets (Eposi, 2021,p.177). Hameed et al., (2022,p.639) acknowledged that optimization of performance lies at the heart of any organization’s survival. Optimization focuses on improving strategies and reaching customers using data analytics (Anindya and Irawan, 2025:157). Digitization can help managers in supporting responsive decision-making and data-driven decisions (Jayadi, 2024).

Moran et al., (2024,p.3) corroborated the assertion that digital transformation of operational processes utilizes data management to guide decision making. This may mean that technology optimizes operations and, at the same time, creates backup systems in case networks are compromised. To further optimize operations, the South African Post Office Information Technology section should be responsible for performing regular information backup and develop a procedure for testing backups to restore data from being lost (South African Post Office Information and Technology Policy, 2023,p.56). Mello (2015,p.246) further wrote that restructuring involves an evaluation of the strength and weaknesses of the organization, and this process increasingly forces management to optimize operations by minimizing weaknesses. Boccia, Ditch, Gattuso and Greszler (2020,p.6) opined that postal administrators should make operational changes to operate sustainably and competitively to achieve organizational objectives.

3.1.2 Conceptual framework for the digital transformation of the postal sector.

increase in revenue growth and high productivity. Furthermore, the use of internal and external resources is not sufficient; the framework suggests that resources should be digitized, and e-services should be considered to optimize operations. Ulrich-Diener, Dvoulety and Spacek (2025) postulated that in a quickly changing banking space, companies have insufficient financial resources and, therefore, digitization could lead to improved profit and increased production. This statement is in line with Umar and Balewa (2023,p.5), as well as Puspitasari and Sutianingsih (2025,p.606), who contended that digitization is an essential and economically suitable strategy that organizations apply to integrate scarce resources such as money, assets, and employees (Junior and Kamiienskie,

2021). Samambert and Khouangvichit (2025,p.9) wrote that at some stage Deutsche Post, Poste Italiane, and Royal Mail reviewed their strategies, and most services were digitized, particularly around the Internet, email, and m-commerce, and digital knowledge is the key to success.

3.1.3 Infrastructure Development

A key product is the development of infrastructure that makes the postal network available to retailers to sell their products at post offices, while courier operators will be able to use the network to deliver parcels in areas where they do not operate (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024,p.33). South Africa struggles to provide and maintain infrastructure that allows the industrial, commercial, and household sectors to function effectively, according to the Auditor General's report in Eposi (2021,p.52). For this reason, organizations in this case, the Post Offices need to invest in a robust infrastructure that supports organizational goals (Mahlangu and Schutte, 2024). Similarly, Ittmann (2023) confirmed that postal networks and infrastructure are among the key tools for inclusiveness and sustainable prosperity in global economies. Similarly, Jayadi (2024,p.11) affirmed that companies work in a complex way and deal with many challenges, including poor infrastructure, and digitization produces another expensive challenge, such as Information Technology infrastructure. One of the reasons is that these three companies can face common challenges such as regulatory barriers and infrastructure limits (Samambet and Khouangvichit, 2025). South African Post Office Annual Report (2023,p.39) emphasized that the state of the Information Technology infrastructure remains a serious risk to the organization and that there has been no significant investment in Information Technology infrastructure in the past 11 years (South African Post Office Information Technology Policy, 2023,p.55). In my opinion, infrastructure development pays way for improved service delivery and increases the reputation of the entity because individuals may not want to invest their assets in an infrastructure that is not developed.

3.1.4 Payment channel modernization

In today's business environment, where competition is very high, institutions must introduce new products and alternative ways of paying for products (Mavlutova et al., 2021). The use of information communication technology by citizens in paying service charges could ensure convenience and minimise long queues (Maleka, 2016:170). According to the SAPO Corporate Plan (2024,p.44), the Post Office has decided to pay for products and services online and in the palm of a consumer's hand (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023). The South African Post Office Information Technology Policy (2023,p.32) showed that it is the responsibility of the South African Post Office to inform customers of transactions relating to payments. This suggests that to increase revenue and improve service delivery, entities need to invest in an advanced payment method convenient for customers. It is in this context that Deutsche Post must price basic postal services equitably nationally to discourage anti-competitive actions and keep mail inexpensive. (Samambet and Khouangvichit, 2025,p.13).

3.1.5 Workforce and Reskilling Plan

Organizational restructuring leads to job losses (Umar and Balewa, 2023,p.1). Reengineering the organization's products and services requires an upgrading of the workforce (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024,p.24-25). A skill shortage is a source of aggravation for firms and, when severe, is likely to affect the quality and quantity related to the output of the organization (Richardson in Eposi, 2021,p.172). Mello and Makamu (2021:648) have concluded that organizations that manage their employees effectively and efficiently are likely to achieve their goals, and skilling becomes paramount. Bakar et al., (2020,p.79) have concluded that failure to adapt to the new digital knowledge leads to an increased loss to the organization. Loss of critical expertise and experience has harmed the effectiveness of the post office, as well as the appropriate match of skills for the implementation of the strategy (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023,p.67). The fully operational digitalized system required front-line workers and managers with digital mindset and fluency (Mergel in Samambet and Khouangvichit, 2025,p.12). Furthermore, Mergel in Samambet and Khouangvichit, 2025,p.12) also observed that front-line workers were trained on the working of new technologies and how to switch between different types of technologies, creating efficiency gains, and using various digital tools to reduce red tape. This may mean that the introduction of technology necessitates the re-skilling of staff members to be in line with technological developments.

Training and awareness are a crucial pillar that enables Information and Technology users to adapt to new technological developments (Mahlangu and Schutte, 2024). Mello (2015,p.386) corroborated the assertion that reskilling involves a kind of change to employees on how they do their job and how they interact with fellow employees (Rajpakse, 2024:11). Moran et al., (2024,p.2) confirmed that technology allows human work to be complemented and enriched. Moran et al., (2020) further explained that effective organizational management requires strategic planning for staffing and placing employees in roles where their performance is maximized. Mello (2015,p.249) postulated that restructuring involves the transfer of technical skills. The South African Post

Office confirmed that recruitment efforts have been hampered by the lack of funds and a moratorium on appointments and the percentage of Information and Technology vacancies is at 68 percent (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023,p.39). Organizations should make enough budget available for training to reskill their employees for superior performance (Eposi (2021).

3.1.6 Efficient Use of Scarce Resources

Corporate restructuring is an essential and economically suitable strategy that organizations apply to integrate scarce resources such as money, assets, and employees (Umar and Balewa, 2023,p.5). Yuen and Lim in Eposi (2021,p.48) alerted us to the fact that in some cases, organizational resources such as finances and human resources are not placed in the right positions for entities to attain organizational goals. Bakar et al., (2020, p.79) wrote that restructuring guards against overlapping resources and cost containment. Anjomshoae in Jayadi (2024,p.2) correctly argued that managers should be more accountable and transparent in using limited resources effectively and efficiently. Puspitasari and Sutianingsih affirmed that restructuring assists in metrics that measure the efficiency of using resources, especially labour, in the production process. Moran et al., (2024,p.4) confirmed that restructuring can help companies save 30% of resources, and operational costs could be significantly reduced. Likewise, Mello (2015:249) asserted that restructuring involves cost savings (Sides and Cuevas, 2020). It is against this background that this may suggest that streamlining resources could save costs, improve service delivery, and enforce accountability.

In addition to corporate restructuring as a strategy to improve service delivery in the South African Post Office, the Performance Management System, as a business strategic intervention, assists the polity in improving service delivery and increasing revenue levels.

3.2 Performance Management Process as a pillar strategy utilized by the South African Post Office to improve service delivery

Like all other state-owned companies, the South African Post Office uses performance management to deal with performance issues within its workplace. Mello (2015,p.439) correctly argued that the Performance Management System in the workplace facilitates employee development by assessing deficiencies in performance levels and skills, and for the organization to determine specific training interventions. During performance discussions, managers clarify what they expect individuals and groups to do, and individuals and teams communicate their expectations to their principals (Eposi, 2021). Puspitasari and Sutianingsih (2025,p.606) explained that continuous planning, measurement, evaluation and development, individual and team performance, can be optimally improved. To bring uniformity and certainty on how performance issues should unfold, the Post Office has developed the Performance Management policy of 1998, which is to be used as a guideline by all stakeholders involved with the performance process. This 1998 SAPO performance policy must be applied in line with the revised performance management policy (2017) to put performance in the Post Office in the right perspective. South African Post Office Performance Management Policy lists the following phases that are to be followed to complete a full performance management process (South African Post Office Performance Management Policy, 2008):

3.2.1 Performance planning

Beginning at the start of the performance year, performance planning is the first stage of the performance management cycle (SAPO Performance Management Policy, 2017,p.5).

Puspitasari and Sutianingsih (2025,p.607) regarded performance planning as an approach of managing performance involving setting performance goals for the organization and individuals, monitoring performance delivery, and providing feedback (Martin, 2009,p.187). In the planning phase, both the manager and the employee sit down and agree on the goals (Kalogiannidis et al., 2025,p.237). Similarly, in SAPO, the first stage in the SAPO performance management process is the planning phase (SAPO Performance Management Policy, 2008). In this phase, the performance manager and his subordinate work together to draft a performance contract that includes strategic goals, key performance indicators (KPIs), measurable evaluation criteria, action and development plans (Anindya and Irawan, 2025).

In this phase, the employer and the employee can draft a performance contract and agree on the expectations to be met. Inter alia, the performance contract should contain what is to be achieved, how it is to be achieved, why it is to be achieved, and when it is to be achieved. Then a performance contract should be signed by both the employer and the employee as an agreement on what has been agreed.

3.2.2 Performance observation and feedback

Amos et al., (2019,p. 322) indicated that the process of providing performance feedback can be intimidating to the manager, especially when having to provide negative feedback. This is a phase where the performance is observed closely and compared with what has been contracted with the individual (McMillan and Schumacher,

2010,p.193). This phase helps to ensure timely and constructive feedback (Jayadi, 2024:3). Continuous feedback fosters a culture of collaboration and adaptability critical in a dynamic business environment (Idrus, 2025,p.222). Furthermore, Idrus (2025:228) emphasized that performance management helps address unconscious biases and ensures that all employees receive equal growth opportunities (Armstrong, 2010,p.260, Mello, 2015,p. 690-691).

The employer provides the employee with feedback on his/her performance during the past quarter (Kalogiannidis et al., 2025). The manager/supervisor will also guide, assist, and remove all possible obstacles for the incumbent (SAPO Performance Management Policy, 2008). In this phase, the employee may get the opportunity to raise concerns if any, and the two parties may come with plans to mitigate those concerns. The feedback session is a private matter, and only the employee and the supervisors should be involved (Makamu and Mello, 2021).

3.2.3 Performance review

In conducting performance reviews, managers usually ensure that laid goals and targets are followed. Dibua and Uzoka (2025,p.116). Amos et al., (2019) affirmed that in this phase, performance data collected is reviewed and the objectives are agreed for the next performance cycle (Darmawan, 2024,p.52; Puspitarasi and Sutianingsih (2025:606). In the South African Post Office, formal performance reviews are held in June, September, December, and March (South African Post Office Performance Management Policy, 2018). At this stage, both parties have had enough opportunity to provide input in the process. The master-servant roles should not influence the employee to accept everything the supervisor says passively if the incumbent disagrees. Supervisors and managers should encourage employees to participate in the review process and respect performance results (Jayadi, 2024, p.3). Although the review process commences in June in the current year and is completed in March the following year, informal reviews should take place continuously to inform employees of the potential areas of nonconformances (Mello, 2015). Idrus (2025, p.225) explained that continuous reviews adapt to individual needs, offering personalized guidance and support (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2009,p.292).

Furthermore, in the review phase, feedback is presented to the incumbent, who is informed of the areas that need improvement (Amos et al., 2019). Viterouli in Idrus (2025,p.222) has a divergent view and explained that traditional annual performance reviews are facing criticism for their ineffectiveness in fostering real-time improvement and delayed feedback. To avoid criticisms, Khumalo (2022) wrote that feedback should be immediate and constructive and is not meant to destroy or show seniority and power to the incumbent. In organizations, performance reviews can improve productivity by rationalizing systems and processes, increasing responsibility, and encouraging good behaviour. Feedback clarifies uncertainty and increases the morale of employees to gear up for the upcoming performance (Barros, 2025).

3.2.4 Performance evaluation

During this session, the year's performance is formalized by comparing performance with the goals set during the planning phase, a final performance mark is awarded accordingly, and the contracted development actions of the year are addressed (Natsir et al., 2024,p.147 and Khumalo, 2022,p.1). Performance evaluation is like performance assessment (Kumar and Prabhakar, 2018). Hameed et al., (202,p.640) indicated that organizations should evaluate employee performance through performance measurement approaches and set up appropriate strategies to achieve goals (Mello, 2015, p.444). It is in this context that Natsir, Ramli and Putra (2024, p.147) emphasized performance evaluation as a process that involves regular employee performance assessments, providing feedback, and recognizing achievements to optimize performance and guide improvements (Barros, 2025,p.4; Puspitasari and Sutianingsih, 2025,p.606). It is suggested that performance strategies should be incorporated within the Performance Management System, and an online performance Management System may be better as it could eliminate performance biases. Jayadi (2024,p.6) explained that digitizing performance evaluation enables information sharing and improves collaboration among participants conducting performance measurement activities. In this phase, scores are awarded to each category of performance, and a portfolio of evidence is required to arrive at the justification of the allocated mark (Performance Management Policy, South African Post Office, 2008).

3.2.5 Performance Development

This is the final stage of the South African Post Office's performance management procedure. (SAPO Performance Management Policy, 2008). The line manager and the incumbent must identify the development areas together and complete a development plan for the employee accordingly (Amos et al., 2019:6,p.64). Line managers should identify the development areas of all employees and submit this information to the Human Resources Division to act accordingly (Mello, 2015).

The South African Post Office's Human Resource Division should be included since employee development is directly related to their primary responsibilities, and this division typically handles funding for training and development initiatives (South African Post Office Performance Management Policy, 2008).

Gustiawan and Purwanti cited by Idrus (2025:225), explained that organizations can enhance employee development, drive engagement, and foster a culture of continuous improvement, ultimately achieving sustainable competitive advantage (Anindya and Irawan, 2025,p.157). This phase should be a continuous process and not an “event”. Carter, Giber, and Goldsmith (2001,p.299) wrote that performance management is designed to support development planning (Kumar and Prabhakar, 2018,p.178). This notion is reinforced by Kalogiannidas et al., (2025,p.240), who affirmed that proper training enables employees to gain the right knowledge and skills to work most efficiently, thereby enhancing the performance of the organization.

In my opinion, the South African Post Office's performance management process may involve all the phases outlined above, from the planning phase up to the performance development phase, and the phases complete a performance cycle. The operationalization of the Performance Management System, if well implemented, it becomes a good business strategy to improve service delivery and increase profit margins. Furthermore, the Performance Management System also assists with the cross-utilization of scarce resources, which are most of the time limited. Mello (2015,p.689) stated that the implementation of the performance management and development system in the public sector follows a cycle, which begins on 1 April and ends at the end of March of the ensuing year, and this performance cycle is deliberately linked to the financial year for purposes of planning and eases administration (Dibua and Uzoka, 2025,p.120).

4. Methodology

Quinlan, Carr, Griffin, and Zikmund (2024,p.3) refer to methodology as the overall approach to the research project, how the research is carried out, indicating the philosophical foundations of the research project, and guiding decisions around the data gathering methods to be used (Du Plooy, 2009,p.21). The study used both qualitative and quantitative methods to achieve its objectives. The mixed-methods approach was used to collect data. The research methodology adopted in the study fits both qualitative and quantitative studies. These two methodological approaches aimed to understand the role of corporate restructuring in the South African Post Office, Waterberg district. To probe some aspects pertaining to the research questions and research objectives, a qualitative study approach was used, and a semi-structured interview was conducted with the District Manager of Waterberg, trade union representatives, and Post Office customers.

For quantitative data, questionnaires were distributed to Post Office employees, Branch Managers, Human resource practitioners, Tellers, managers, and supervisors. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, with “undecided” as a neutral point, was used to solicit data from the respondents.

5. Results and discussions

The results and discussion in this article are based on two variables, which are restructuring and optimization of resources. The results are presented individually as follows:

5.1 Restructuring Assists in Improving the Performance of the Employees in SAPO

1. Restructuring Assist in Improving the Performance of the Employees in SAPO					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	6,3	6,3	6,3
	Disagree	17	21,5	21,5	27,8
	Undecided	11	13,9	13,9	41,8
	Agree	28	35,4	35,4	77,2
	Strongly Agree	18	22,8	22,8	100,0
	Total	79	100,0	100,0	

This table presents the opinions of the 79 employees regarding whether the restructuring initiatives assist in improving the performance of employees within SAPO. All 79 respondents provided valid answers to this question.

A clear majority of employees believe that restructuring **does** assist in improving employee performance:

- **28 individuals agreed** with the statement, representing **35.4%** of the sample.
- **18 individuals Strongly Agreed**, representing **22.8%** of the sample.

Combined, **58.2%** of the employees hold a positive view regarding the impact of restructuring on employee performance.

A notable portion of employees expressed negative views or uncertainty:

- **17 individuals disagreed**, representing **21.5%** of the sample.
- **5 individuals Strongly Disagreed**, representing **6.3%** of the sample.
- **11 individuals were Undecided**, representing **13.9%** of the sample.

In summary, while most employees perceive restructuring as beneficial for improving employee performance, a significant minority hold negative views or remain uncertain about its impact. This suggests that the perceived effectiveness of restructuring may not be universally shared across the workforce.

5.2 The graphic representation below responds to the variable of whether restructuring assists in improving the performance of the employees in SAPO

Views on whether restructuring optimizes the resources of the Post Office

A question was posed to assess whether restructuring optimizes the resources of the Post Office. The question emanates from the understanding that optimization minimizes cost, improves efficiency, and increases profit margins. The respondents in this study area indicated as follows:

5.3 Restructuring Optimizes Resources of the Post Office

2. Performance Management Optimizes Resources of the Post Office					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	3,8	3,8	3,8
	Disagree	6	7,6	7,6	11,4
	Undecided	12	15,2	15,2	26,6
	Agree	28	35,4	35,4	62,0

Strongly Agree	30	38,0	38,0	100,0
Total	79	100,0	100,0	

This table presents the opinions of the 79 employees regarding whether the Performance Management initiatives optimize the resources of the Post Office. All 79 respondents provided valid answers to this question.

A strong majority of employees believe that restructuring **does** optimize the Post Office's resources:

- **30 individuals Strongly Agreed** with the statement, representing **38.0%** of the sample.
- **28 individuals Agreed**, representing **35.4%** of the sample.

Combined, a significant **73.4%** of the employees hold a positive view regarding the impact of restructuring on resource optimization.

A smaller portion of employees expressed negative views or uncertainty:

- **6 individuals Disagreed**, representing **7.6%** of the sample.
- **3 individuals Strongly Disagreed**, representing **3.8%** of the sample.
- **12 individuals were Undecided**, representing **15.2%** of the sample.

In summary, the data indicate a strong consensus among employees that the performance management efforts are contributing to a more optimized allocation and utilization of the Post Office's resources. This suggests a perceived efficiency gain because of the restructuring process. It is in this context that Hameed et al., (2022,p.639) acknowledged that optimization of performance lies at the centre of any organization's continued existence.

5.4 The graphic representation below responds to the variable whether performance management optimizes the resources of the Post Office

6. Recommendations

It is against this background that the following recommendations were made:

6.1 A need to restructure the post office to improve service delivery

Emanating from the findings of the study, there is a critical need for the Post Office to restructure its operations in the Waterberg District to improve service delivery. In the Post Office context, restructuring should begin from the time when a letter is posted until the same letter is received by the client. Post Office Managers should revisit postal operations by redesigning, modifying, restructuring, and enhancing systems, workflows and work procedural to allow operations to improve the performance of the branches. Areas of inefficiency should be identified and removed. Operational technological equipment should be considered, as some of the old machines will be declared redundant and should be replaced by advanced, reliable, and more efficient machines. It should be noted that restructuring is expensive, and there are serious financial implications involved. Restructuring should be budgeted to make it possible; however, there will be some serious savings in the long run. Moran et al., (2024,p.4) confirmed that restructuring can help companies save 30% of resources, and operational costs

could be significantly reduced. It is in this context that it is recommended that the restructuring of the Post Office be given priority to increase service delivery and revenue growth.

6.2 Optimization of resources

Emanating from this study, there is a need to optimize the resources in the Post Office, particularly in the Waterberg district. It is good business practice that all employees should strive to optimize resources to improve service delivery, irrespective of the position they hold in the company. In this study, there is a strong consensus among employees that the performance management efforts are contributing to a more optimized allocation and utilization of the Post Office's resources. It is in this context that Hameed et al., (2022,p.639) acknowledged that optimization of resources lies at the Centre of any organization's continued existence. It is against this background that optimization of resources should be encouraged to improve service delivery and optimize profit margins.

7. Conclusion

The study confirmed that the South African Post Office is experiencing a drop in revenue. Emanating from the study. There is a need to restructure this entity to enhance service delivery and improve the financial position of the Post Office. This study showed that, among others, the advantages of the restructuring process include infrastructure development, optimization of operations, payment modernization, efficient usage of resources, and reskilling of employees on technology-related matters. The study further showed that performance management plays a significant role in the optimization usage of the allocated resources.

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